

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Propyl Mandelate by Molecular Bromine*

D. KAUSHIK, R. K. MALKANI and G. V. BAKORE

Department of Chemistry, University of Udaipur, Udaipur (India)

Manuscript received 17 April 1979, revised 18 June 1980, accepted 25 August 1980

The oxidation of propyl mandelate by molecular bromine gives benzaldehyde. The reaction is first order with respect to bromine and follows Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics with respect to substrate. This indicates that the reaction proceeds through the complex between the ester and the bromine. The rate is decreased by the addition of bromide ions only to the extent that the bromide ions convert free bromine into inactive tribromide ions. This confirms that the molecular bromine is the active oxidant species. The effect of solvent composition and acidity dependence of the oxidation rate suggests the base catalysis of the reaction. The energy of activation and entropy of activation have values 11.4 ± 0.6 kcal mole⁻¹ and -39.8 ± 2 cal degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively. A mechanism which satisfactorily correlates all the experimental facts have been proposed.

THE kinetics of the oxidation of mandelic acid and of ethyl, *p*-chloro-mandelate with bromine and with hypobromous acid has been studied by Auckett and Barker¹. These authors conclude that for these reactions molecular bromine is the effective oxidant and that the ester behaves like a secondary alcohol. Our preliminary results on the oxidation of propyl mandelate by molecular bromine showed that the product of this oxidation is benzaldehyde. This indicates that propyl mandelate does not behave as a secondary alcohol as concluded by Auckett and Barker¹. We have, therefore, investigated the reaction of propyl-mandelate with molecular bromine in greater details. The results of this investigations are given below.

Experimental

(a) *Material used*: Propyl-mandelate was prepared by Fischer Method². Analytic reagent grade bromine was used without further purification. Acetic acid (B. D. H.) was purified by the method described by Eichelberger and LaMer³. Other chemicals used were of analytical grade specifications.

(b) *Kinetic measurements*: Because of the limited solubility of propyl-mandelate in water the reaction was carried out in aqueous acetic acid solutions. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$); *pH* was adjusted by neutralizing the acetic acid in the solution by sodium hydroxide.

The oxidation capacity of bromine was measured by titration with standardised solution of sodium thiosulphate.

(c) *Product study*: The product study was made under kinetic conditions. The oxidised mixture was completely neutralized by aqueous sodium bicarbonate and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was heated on a water bath to remove the ether, cooled, made acidic and 2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine (in 2*N* hydrochloric acid) solution was added. The precipitate of 2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative was recrystallized and found to have m.p. 236-237° and m.m.p. 235-237°. This shows that benzaldehyde is the product of oxidation

Results and Discussion

The order with respect to bromine is one for nearly 60 percent of the reaction at constant bromide ion concentration. A plot of inverse of first order rate constant versus inverse of ester concentration gives a straight line which cuts the rate constant axis. This indicates a complex formation between ester and bromine. At constant ester concentration the first order rate constant decreases with increase in bromide ion concentration. A plot of inverse of first order rate constant versus bromide ion concentration gives a straight line. This shows that the rate of the reaction can be expressed as:

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k[\text{Ester}] \times K'[\text{Br}_2] \text{Total}}{\{(1/K) + [\text{Ester}]\} \{K' + [\text{Br}^-]\}}$$

where *K* is the formation constant of the complex between the ester and bromine and *K'* is the dissociation constant for the reaction $\text{Br}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Br}_2 + \text{Br}^-$. From the data given in Table 1 the value of the formation constant *K* can be estimated. This works

* Presented at Annual convention of Chemists (1977) held at Jaipur.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF ESTER CONCENTRATION AND BROMIDE CONCENTRATION ON RATE

Solvent composition : 50 per cent acetic acid
50 per cent water (v/v)

[Ester] × 10 ³ moles litre ⁻¹	pH=3.3 [Br ⁻] moles litre ⁻¹	Temperature=35°C k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹
2.0	0.05	5.76
2.0	0.10	4.15
2.0	0.15	3.10
2.0	0.20	2.45
4.0	0.05	9.60
6.0	0.05	12.8
8.0	0.05	15.2

out to be 10.9 ± 0.6 mole lit⁻¹. Similarly the dissociation constant K' can also be estimated from this data, the value of K' comes out to be 0.058 ± 0.005 moles lit⁻¹. This value of dissociation constant agrees well with the value reported earlier⁴. The effect of bromide ion on rate clearly shows that molecular bromine is the active oxidant under experimental conditions⁵.

Increase of pH increases the rate of reaction in the pH range 3.0 to 5.0 (Table 2). At constant pH the rate decreases with increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent mixture (Table 3). These results can be explained on the basis of base catalysis, for the disproportionation of the complex between ester and bromine (hypobromite ester).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF pH ON THE RATE OF REACTION

Solvent composition : 70 per cent acetic acid
30 per cent water (v/v)

[Ester]=2.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [Br ₂]=2.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	[Br ⁻]=5.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	Temperature=35°C			
pH	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	3.3	3.9	4.4	5.0
		3.20	4.17	5.48	7.49

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF RATE OF REACTION WITH PERCENTAGE ACETIC ACID

[Ester]=2.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [Br ₂]=2.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	[Br ⁻]=5.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	pH=3.3 Temperature=35°C			
Percentage acetic acid	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	40	50	60	70
		7.83	5.76	4.10	3.20

The reaction was carried out at different temperatures (Table 4). The values of energy of activation and entropy of activation for this reaction have been estimated from the temperature effect. These values are $\Delta E^* = 11.4 \pm 0.6$ kcal mole⁻¹ and $\Delta S^* = -39.8 \pm 2$ cal. degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹.

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH TEMPERATURE

Solvent composition : 70 per cent acetic acid
30 per cent water (v/v)

[Ester]=6.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [Br ₂]=1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	[Br ⁻]=1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	pH=3.3			
Temperature °	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	303	308	315	318
		4.13	5.30	7.14	10.0

These results can be accommodated on the basis of the following mechanism :

This is probably the first report of the formation of the complex of the ester and the bromine which in a slow irreversible step gives the hypobromite ester of the mandelic acid. The type of complex proposed here is similar to the one proposed by Barker, Overrend and Rees⁶ for the reaction of β-D-glucose and bromine. The hypobromite ester of mandelic acid undergoes a base catalysed reaction giving benzaldehyde.

References

1. P. AUCKETT and I. R. L. BARKER, *J. Chem. Soc. Per. Trans.*, 1973, II, 965.
2. E. FISCHER and A. S. SPIER, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 3252.
3. W. C. EICHELBERGER and V. K. LAMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 3633.
4. D. B. SCAIFE and H. J. V. TYRRELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 386.
5. B. PERLMUTTER-HAYMAN and A. PERSKY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 276.
6. I. R. L. BARKER, W. O. OVERREND and C. W. REES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3254.